

**THE USE AND DEVELOPMENT OF ARCHIVAL DESCRIPTION
STANDARDS: AN ASSESSMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE
INTERNATIONAL COUNCIL ON ARCHIVES AND THE SOCIETY OF
AMERICAN ARCHIVISTS**

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Introduction: The International Council on Archives (ICA) organizes the international process of regulating the description of and access to archival contents and establishing the theoretical foundations used in the representation of information. Within the framework of this mission, ICA started to work on preparing the Statement of Principles Regarding Archival Description in 1988. ICA completed and published this study in 1992, thereby making it known to the professional community [1].

1. An Overview of Archival Description Principles and Standards

The principles of the Statement of Principles Regarding Archival Description, which determines the purposes of the description in archival, are as follows [1; 2, P. 388]:

- To establish standardization in the definition of archival material.
- To make clear and relevant definitions of the description rules of archival material.
- Facilitate access to archival material and exchange of information.

- To encourage the exchange of authorization data (in accordance with the legislation) and the integration of definitions made by different archives/institutions within an integrated information system.

Following these principles, ICA has published four international standards that have a direct impact on archival communities in all countries. These are listed below:

- 1) ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description.
- 2) ISAAR(CPF): International Standard Archival Authority Record for Corporate Bodies, Persons, and Families.
- 3) ISDF: International Standard for Describing Functions.
- 4) ISDIAH: International Standard for Describing Institutions with Archival Holdings.

The four standards given above relate to data structures to be used internationally to define records, records producers, functions and institutions holding archival records [2, P. 388-389]. In 2012, ICA established the Expert Group on Archival Description (EGAD) with members from 12 countries, which replaced the Committee for Good Practices and Standards. This group of representatives from twelve different countries developed an international conceptual model for archival description. This group published the first draft of the conceptual model in September 2016 under the title *Records in Contexts: A Conceptual Model for Archival Description (RiC-CM)*; It published its second draft in 2021. In the preparation of EGAD, conceptual models developed in Australia, New Zealand, Spain and Finland were analyzed. In addition, the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) developed for libraries and the Reference Model of the International Committee on Conceptual Documentation of the International Council of Museums (CIDOC-CRM) developed for museums were also examined.

Thus, it has prepared a model suitable for archival principles and the needs of institutions. The main aim of RiC-CM has been to complement and link the four international description norms and adapt to the new possibilities offered by information and communication technologies to integrate data and services into the web [2, P. 391]. ICA, through EGAD, has brought a new vision and methodology to

archival description by developing RiC-CM, a conceptual model that will replace existing archival description standards. RiC-CM has a multi-dimensional representation and allows information items to be arranged in the form of graphics. Defined entities are described as nodes that are interconnected by the relations among them. In addition to the RiC-CM context model, which includes the definition of entities, attributes, and relationships, EGAD is developing an ontology called Records-Ontology in Contexts (RiC-O). RiC-O is a technical description of RiC-CM. In the technical description, entities, attributes, and relationships are encoded and technically mapped in a network form as a data model. RiC-O basically depicts the vocabulary and formalities of the concept model and primarily aims to create data records with the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [3]. In Switzerland and Austria, ISAD (G) and, in part, ISAAR (CPF), as recommended by ICA, have been adopted as the basis for national standards developed and adopted by professional associations. In France, Spain, England, USA, Australia and Canada, ISAD (G) and ISAAR (CPF) form the basis of national standards [3]. In Germany, studies were carried out on code standards for archival description within the framework of the cooperation between the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin and the Society of American Archivists (SAA). Today, there are four international standards for describing archival records, their context with the producer institution of documents in archives, and institutions with archival collections. There are also three associated communication standards for encoding archival description to create, maintain or exchange information according to description standards. With the development of these standards and conceptual modeling of records, a new and comprehensive approach has been achieved [3]. Therefore, the standards that make archival definition possible are made by ICA, and the studies to code archival definition and provide communication are made by SAA and they are becoming widespread.

2. Archival Description Standards Developed by ICA

Archival standards are the standards that are accepted and used at the national and international levels, developed by national or international organizations in the field of archival science. Examples of international organizations are the International

Organization for Standardization (ISO), Committee on Best Practice & Standards (ICA CBPS), and the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) for web-based standards. The American National Standards Institute (ANSI), British Standards Institution (BSI), Society of American Archivists (SAA) or national archives in some countries can be given as examples to national standardization organizations. The standards developed and published by ICA, an international organization on archival description standards, since 1988 are given in Table 1 [4].

Table 1

ICA's Standards for Archival Description

Standard	Edition	Development Year(s)	Publication Year
Statement of Principles Regarding Archival Description		(1988) 1989-1992	1992
ISAD (G)	1.	1990-1993	1994
ISAAR	1.	1993-1995	1996
ISAD (G)	2.	1996-2000	1999
ISAAR (CPF)	2.	2000-2004	2004
ISDF	1.	2005-2007	2007
ISDIAH	1.	2005-2008	2008
RiC		2012-	

2.1. ISAD(G)

The ISAD(G) standard was prepared in the 1990s, and in 2000 the second edition was redesigned with appropriate updates. Based on a standard, one-dimensional and multi-level approach, information elements are arranged hierarchically, starting from the most general level, the records fonds, to the most specific element representing the records (from the part to the whole) [5, P. 12].

2.2. ISAAR(CPF)

The ISAAR(CPF) specifies the types of information that can be included in an archive authority. ISAAR(CPF) provides guidance on how these types can be deployed in an archival description system [6, P. 11].

2.3. ISDF

This standard specifies the types of information that can be included in the definitions of functions and provides guidance on how such definitions can be applied in an archival information system [7, P. 11].

2.4. ISDIAH

The main purpose of ISDIAH is to facilitate the definition of institutions whose primary function is to keep archives and make them available to the public. This standard or a suitable subset of its elements can be applied to any organization that provides access to the records that they save. In addition, this standard introduces provisions for linking information about institutions to the descriptions of the records that they hold and those who produce them [8, P. 9].

2.5. RiC-CM

ICA's first purpose with RiC-CM (Records in Contexts) is to combine existing ISAD(G), ISAAR, ISDF and ISDIAH standards to which changes are added reflecting new concepts observed in the field of archival practice. While centralizing the models makes it easier for archivists to understand and use the standard, it also standardizes the tools that support the description of the archive [9, P. 2].

Figure 1

Key Assets of the RiC-CM Conceptual Model

(Source: International Council on Archives Expert Group on Archival Description, [ICA-EGAD], 2021)

RiC-CM includes the agent that produces the records from ISAAR. The producing structure can be a person, group, family, institutional structure, position (role between individuals and group), representative of the producing structure. Functions are taken from ISDF and included in RiC-CM. Functions include purpose, activity and operational processes.

3. Archival Description Standards Developed by SAA

There are three basic archival description or communication standards developed by the Archivists Association of America in the United States. These are Describing Archives: A Content Standard (2nd ed) (DACS) [10], Encoded Archival Description (EAD) [11] and Encoded Archival Context Corporate Bodies, Persons, and Families (EAC-CPF) [12]. These standards are the standards that are the implementation and extension of ISAD(G) at the national level [13, P. 25].

3.1. DACS

DACS is designed to include access to and catalog records of archival descriptions. It was revised in 2013. This revision takes into account the increasing convergence between the descriptive standards for archive, library and museum institutions. In particular, the publication and adoption of the RDA (Resource Description and Access) found value in this revision. Also in this revision, the need to provide guidance on the development and adoption of RDA as well as EAD3 and the establishment of archival authority records was addressed [14, P. vi].

3.2. EAD

EAD (Encoded Archival Description) is an ISAD(G) based archive description communication standard [15]. EAD is a standard metadata transfer application for archive records. EAD, introduced in 1998, underwent a major revision and became EAD3 in 2015. The SAA Standards Committee oversaw the latest revision by the SAA Standards Committee's Technical Subcommittee for Encoded Archival Description, SAA TS-EAD [13, p. 26].

3.3. EAC-CPF

The EAC-CPF primarily addresses the description of individuals, families, and institutional structures that create, maintain, use, and are responsible for and/or variously associated with records. It supports linking information about an agent to other agents and linking to descriptions of documents and other context entities to show/discover relationships between records-creating entities. EAC-CPF is a communication framework for contextual archival information for individuals, legal entities and families.

Conclusion

In archival description, the structure, content and context of the records provide the principles of physical and intellectual control over the records. These principles make archives easier to both understand and have access to. A new archival description standard is being developed by ICA. It is thought that this developed standard will replace the previous four standards ISAD(G), ISAAR(CPF), ISDF and ISDIAH. The mentioned standards are related to the structural and content parts of the records. RiC-CM reflects the context of the records. Therefore, ICA RiC-CM is the development over time using archival description standards to ensure the structural, contentwise and contextual integrity of the records.

ISAD(G) provides guidance for the definition of fonds and their component parts. ISAAR(CPF) provides guidance for the creation of authority information about the creators of archival materials. ISDF provides guidance for the description of record creators' functions. The purpose of ISDIAH is a separate standardized description of archive owners to make an archive information system more useful. The use of archival standards enables both the integration of archiving activities with information technologies and the easier adoption of new applications. EAD, EAD3 and DACS, which were prepared by SAA for the adoption and implementation of ISAD (G), especially in the USA, formed the communication language of ISAD (G). The collaboration of both ICA and SAA in archival description shows that archival description requires several interrelated standards. Obviously, ICA is trying to standardize the basic components of identification with ISAD(G) and their relationship. It also standardized how to ensure the flexibility of the standardized

structure. It has also transformed scope of authority such as geography, country and language into a standard structure. The process of archival description seems to have been completed, with these standardized activities of ICA, with SAA's communication standards representing these standards, and the sharing of information on archival materials between computers and people.

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